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Review Article

**DESIGN, DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION OF
MATRIX TABLET CONTAINING DEXAMETHASONE****Ranjeet Kumar¹, Naveen Gupta¹, Dharmendra Singh Rajput¹**¹Madhyanchal Professional University, Bhopal, M.P.**Abstract:**

The oral route is considered to be most convenient for administration of drugs to patients. Colonic drug delivery is a relatively recent approach to the treatment of diseases such as ulcerative colitis, Crohn's disease and irritable bowel syndrome. Such local treatment has the advantage of requiring smaller drug quantities, possibly leading to a reduced incidence of side effects and drug interactions. Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) is a general term for group of chronic inflammatory disorders of unknown etiology involving the gastrointestinal tract. Since there are no pathognomonic features or specific diagnostic tests, in a strict sense, these disorders remain diagnoses of exclusion. Their features are sufficiently characteristic. However, to permit accurate diagnosis in the majority of cases, chronic IBD may be divided into two major groups chronic non-specific ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease. Matrix tablets, though release a minimal percent of the drug in stomach and small intestine, are the choice for colon-targeting of drugs as their preparation involves less processing variables and are manufactured by direct compression with conventional tableting facilities. It is clear from these results that DXCT2 could target dexamethasone to colon because as it released almost the entire quantity at the end of 24 h of study. The DXCT3 tablets are also considered as potential formulations for targeting of dexamethasone to colon because of the fact that the human caecal contents would be far more rich in enzymatic activity than what was used in the present study. However, the relative potential of formulation DXCT2 and DXCT3 need to be evaluated in human volunteers.

Keywords: Inflammatory bowel disease, ulcerative colitis, crohn's disease, dexamethasone, colon targeted drug delivery

Corresponding author:

Ranjeet Kumar,
Madhyanchal Professional University,
Bhopal, M.P.

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) describes two major chronic, non-specific inflammatory disorders of the gastro-intestinal (GI) tract, ulcerative colitis (UC) and Crohn's disease (CD), the causes of which remain unknown. UC is usually limited to the colon and rectum [1]. The colon and rectum are parts of the body's digestive system which remove nutrients from food and store waste until it passes out of the body. Most of the conventional drug delivery systems for treating the colon disorders such as inflammatory bowel diseases (e.g. irritable bowel syndrome, ulcerative colitis, Crohn's disease etc.) [2], infectious diseases (e.g. amoebiasis) and colon cancer are failing as the drugs do not reach the site of action in appropriate concentrations. Thus, an effective and safe therapy of these colonic disorders, using site-specific drug delivery systems is a challenging task to the pharmaceutical technologists. Colon specific drug delivery systems are designed to obtain targeted drug delivery to the large intestine (colon) [3]. They provide local delivery for the treatment of colonic diseases like inflammatory bowel disease (ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease) and colon cancer, where it is necessary to attain high concentration of the drug. Colonic drug delivery is a relatively recent approach to the treatment of diseases such as ulcerative colitis, Crohn's disease and irritable bowel syndrome. Such local treatment has the advantage of requiring smaller drug quantities, possibly leading to a reduced incidence of side effects and drug interactions [4]. Colon specific diseases are often inefficiently managed by oral therapy, because most orally administered drugs are absorbed before arriving in the colon. Therefore, colon-specific drug delivery systems, which can deliver drugs to the lower gastrointestinal tract without releasing them in the upper GI-tract, can be expected to decrease the side effects of the drugs and improve the quality of life for patients suffering from colon specific diseases. A successful colon-specific drug delivery system is one that remains intact in the physiological environment of stomach and small intestine, but releases the drug in the colon. Different in vitro and in-vivo methods are used to evaluate the colonic drug delivery systems [5-6]. Dexamethasone is a white or almost white odourless crystalline powder, practically insoluble in water; sparingly soluble in alcohol in dehydrated alcohol, in acetone in dioxan, and in methyl alcohol; slightly soluble in chloroform and in dichloromethane; very slightly soluble in ether. Protect from light. Dexamethasone has both anti-inflammatory (glucocorticoid) and salt retaining (mineralocorticoid) properties. Glucocorticoids cause profound and varied metabolic effects. In addition, it

modifies the body's immune responses to diverse stimuli. It is used as replacement therapy in adrenocortical deficiency states and may be used for their anti-inflammatory effects [7]. Dexamethasone is readily absorbed from the GI tract; it is metabolized by the liver, which is the rate-limiting step in its clearance. The metabolism and excretion of the synthetic glucocorticoids generally parallel hydrocortisone. Induction of hepatic enzymes will increase the metabolic clearance of hydrocortisone and the synthetic glucocorticoids. The half-life values refer to the intrinsic activity of each agent; insoluble salts of dexamethasone are used as repository injections and have sustained effect due to delayed absorption from the injection site. Dexamethasone is used principally as an anti-inflammatory or immunosuppressant agent. Because of its only minimal mineralocorticoid properties [8]. The purpose of the current assessment was to develop a formulation for targeting drugs to the colon in a controlled manner for management of inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). The dexamethasone matrix tablets have to manage colonic disease. The proposed drug delivery system provides required amount with minimum side effect at specific site for better treatment with naturally occurring biodegradable polymers for better patient compliance. These adverse effects may be seen in long term administration of glucocorticoids like dexamethasone, other toxic effects are glaucoma, raised intracranial pressure, fever and disorders of menstruation. Therefore, by delivering dexamethasone specially to colon by using colon specific drug delivery system. This may manage side effects as compared to conventional oral administration, thus it becomes necessary to expand the colon specific delivery of dexamethasone in the treatment of inflammatory bowel disease (IBD).

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

Dexamethasone I.P. (98.6-102% purity, M.P. 255°C), Absolute ethanol (purity 99.9%), and distilled water was used in the study. UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Model UV-1201), Shimadzu Corporation, Japan, was used.

Formulation of guar gum-based colon targeted matrix tablets and immediate release tablets:

Matrix tablets of dexamethasone were prepared by direct compression method. Microcrystalline cellulose (Avicel PH-105) was used as diluent, in reference formulation (immediate release dexamethasone tablets) a superdisintegrant such as sodium starch glycolate was incorporated at 5% level for rapid disintegration of tablet and a mixture

of talc and magnesium stearate (2:1) was used as lubricant. Guar gum was included in the colon-targeted formulations in various proportions. The composition of different colon-targeted formulations and immediate release formulation used in the study containing 9 mg of dexamethasone in each formulation is shown in Table 5.1. In all the colon-targeted formulations, guar gum and M.C.C. was sieved (250 μ m) separately and dexamethasone was premixed with small amount of guar gum or M.C.C. and sodium starch glycolate (dry) 5% (in case of immediate release tablet) and magnesium stearate, talc by Spatulation method in glass mortar and pestle followed by mixing of remaining guar gum or M.C.C. (in case of immediate release tablet) by addition method [9].

Evaluation Parameters

Micrometric Evaluation of Powder Mix:

i. Bulk Density: Both loose bulk density (LBD) and tapped bulk density (TBD) were determined. The accurately weighed amount of sample (5gm) taken in a 25 ml measuring cylinder of Borosil measured/recorded the volume of packing and tapped 100 times on a plane hard wooden surface and tapped volume of packing recorded and LBD & TBD calculated by following formula [10].

$$\text{LBD (Loose bulk density)} = \frac{\text{Mass of Powder}}{\text{Volume of Packing}}$$

$$\text{TBD (Tapped bulk density)} = \frac{\text{Mass of Powder}}{\text{Tapped volume of packing}}$$

ii. Percentage compressibility: Percent compressibility of powders mix was determined by Carr's Compressibility Index calculated by following formula (Table 6.6)

$$\text{Carr's Index (\%)} = \frac{\text{TBD} - \text{LBD} \times 100}{\text{TBD}}$$

B. Powders mix drug content uniformity test:

The final powder blend (1 to 3 times unit dose) was sampled using a thief from 10 different locations (5 from top, 3 from middle and 2 from bottom). Powder sample collected mixed properly in a glass mortar and pestle. Accurately weighed 388.88 mg of powder (equivalent to 10 mg dexamethasone) transferred to 50 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in 25 ml absolute ethanol, sonicated, filtered through Whatman filter paper # 41 and made up the volume with distilled water (stock solution). 1 ml from stock solution taken, transferred to 10 ml volumetric flask and volume made up to 10 ml. The absorbance at 242 nm and powder drug content was calculated with the help of standard calibration curve and recorded [11].

Post-Compression Evaluation of Tablets:

The tablets were evaluated for various properties such as the ones enlisted below:

Thickness and Diameter Test:

Thickness and diameter test permits accurate measurement and provides information on the variation between tablets. 5 tablets were taken and the thickness and diameter was measured using dial caliper. The tablets thickness and diameter should be controlled within a $\pm 5\%$ variation of a standard value.

Weight Variation Test:

The procedure described in the I.P. 1996 was employed to determine the weight variation of the tablets. Ten tablets from each formulation were weighed on a electronic balance and the mean weight was taken. The mean weight was calculated. Each tablet was then weighed separately and the standard deviation in weight was calculated for each formulation [12].

Hardness Test:

Hardness indicates the ability of a tablet to withstand mechanical shocks while handling. The hardness of the tablets was determined using the strokes \bar{n} Monsanto hardness tester. It is expressed in kg/cm². In all cases the mean of 10 replicate were determined and the mean and standard deviation values was calculated.

Friability Test:

The friability of the tablets from each formulation was tested by using Campbell Electronics made friabilator. It is expressed in percentage (%). Ten tablets were weighed initially (Winitial) and placed in the friability test apparatus and allowed to fall six inches on each turn of the friabilator at 25 rpm. After four minutes of treatment or 100 revolutions, the tablets were loss due to abrasion or fracture was the measure of tablet friability [13]. The tablets were weighed again (Wfinal). The % friability was then calculated by,

$$F = \frac{W_{\text{final}} - W_{\text{initial}}}{W_{\text{initial}}} \times 100$$

Percent Friability of tablets less than 1% are considered acceptable.

Measurement of Mass Degree of Swelling:

Each tablet from all formulations preweighed and allowed to equilibrate with 100 ml of water for 5 h. The tablets were removed, blotted using tissue paper

and weighed. The mass degree of swelling then was calculated using the formulae:

$$Q = \frac{\text{Mass of the swollen gel}}{\text{Mass of the dry polymer}}$$

in-vitro dissolution study in 0.1N HCl and pH 7.4

Sorensenís Phosphate Buffer: The ability of guar gum matrix tablets of dexamethasone to remain intact in the physiological environment of stomach and small intestine was assessed by conducting drug release studies under conditions mimicking mouth to colon transit. Drug release studies carried out using dissolution rate test apparatus USP XXIII (100 rpm, 37°C) for 2h in 0.1N HCl (900ml). Then the dissolution medium was replaced with pH 7.4 Sorensenís phosphate buffer (900 ml) and tested for drug release for 3 h. At different time intervals, 1 ml of dissolution samples was obtained without pre-filter taken in 10 ml volumetric flask, made up to volume transferred to centrifuged tube and centrifuge at 2500 rpm for 15 min, supernatant liquid was filtered through, G-5 borosil filter and analyzed for dexamethasone content by UV-spectrophotometric method. The susceptibility of the matrix tablets to the enzymatic action of colonic bacteria was assessed by continuing the drug release studies in rat caecal content medium [14].

In-vitro dissolution study in rat caecal content medium:

After conducting the dissolution study in 0.1M HCl (2 h) and pH 7.4 phosphate buffer (3 h), the dissolution study was continued in PBS containing 4% w/v of rat caecal contents. The drug release studies were carried out using dissolution rate test apparatus USPXXIII (Apparatus 1, 100 rpm, 37°C) with slight modifications. A beaker (capacity 150 mL) containing 100 mL of rat caecal content medium was immersed in the water maintained in the 1000mL vessel, which, in turn, was in the water bath of the apparatus. After completing the dissolution study in 0.1N HCl (2h) and pH 7.4 phosphate buffer (3h), the partially swollen guar gum formulations were placed in the baskets of the apparatus and immersed in the rat caecal content medium. As the caecum is naturally anaerobic the experiment was carried out with continuous nitrogen gas supply into the medium to stimulate anaerobic environment of the caecum shown in Plate 5.4. At different time intervals 1 mL of the dissolution sample was taken without prefilter in 10 ml volumetric flask containing 1 mL of absolute ethanol, made up to volume with distilled water, transferred to centrifuge tube, centrifuged at 2500 rpm for 15 min, supernatant liquid was filtered through G-5 borosil filter and analysed for dexamethasone by UV-spectrophotometric method.

The amount of dexamethasone left over in the basket at the end of 24 h of the study was also estimated and added to the cumulative amount of drug released up to 24 h to account for the total drug present in the tablet formulation. Drug release studies in 0.1N HCl (2h), pH 7.4 Sorensenís phosphate buffer (3h) and pH 6.8 PBS without rat Caecal contents (Control study). The in-vitro drug release studies were also carried out in 0.1N HCl (900 mL; 2h), pH 7.4 Sorensenís phosphate buffer (900 mL; 3h) and pH 6.8 PBS without rat caecal contents (100 mL; 19h; control) in order to show that the drug release in rat caecal content medium is because of the colonic bacterial action, and not due to mechanical erosion. This is shown by statistical comparison of the percent of drug release in dissolution medium with and without rat caecal contents [15].

In all the above dissolution studies, the amount of dexamethasone in either the swollen guar gum matrix formulation or in the degraded mass left over in the basket for the dissolution study was estimated by UV-spectrophotometry. Such estimation was carried out for accounting the total amount of drug released into the dissolution medium. (This ensures the estimation of all the finely suspended drug particles that may be released from the guar gum matrix formulation on erosion by colonic bacteria). This was obtained by subtracting the amount of drug left over in the formulation after dissolution study from that of total drug content in the matrix formulation.

The amount of drug in the entire quantity of the dissolution medium, i.e., either 900 ml of 0.1M HCl, 900 mL of pH 7.4 Sorensenís phosphate buffer or 100 mL of rat caecal content medium (Simulated colonic fluid) at the end of 2,5,10,15 and 24 h respectively was estimated by UV-spectrophotometry. In case of drug estimated in 0.1M HCl and pH 7.4 phosphate buffer, the entire quantity of dissolution medium (900 mL) after dissolution study was transferred to 1000 mL volumetric flask containing absolute alcohol (about 25 mL). The contents were sonicated well for complete dissolution of dexamethasone and made up to the volume with distilled water. 1 mL of this mixture was transferred to 10 mL volumetric flask, made up to volume with distilled water, filtered through G-5 borosil (bacteria proof filter) and the filtrate was subjected to UV-analysis as described below.

The drug released in rat caecal content medium was estimated by UV- spectrophotometry as follows. The entire quantity of rat caecal medium (100 ml) at the end of the study was transferred to 250 mL

volumetric flask containing about 25 mL of absolute ethanol. The content was sonicated to completely dissolve the eroded drug particles and made up to volume with distilled water. 1mL of sample from this flask was added to 10mL volumetric flask, made up to volume with distilled water, transferred to centrifuge tubes, centrifuged at 2500 rpm for 15 min, supernatant liquid was filtered through G-5 borosil (bacteria proof filter) and the filtrate was subjected to UV- spectrophotometric analysis as described below [16].

Statistical Analysis:

The cumulative percent of dexamethasone released from guar gum matrix tablets (n=3) at different time periods with and without rat caecal contents was compared. The statistical significance was tested by using student's t-test. A value of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant [17].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The drugs were estimated in the dissolution medium (0.1N HCl). The calibration curves in the various dissolution medium i.e. 0.1N HCl solution, phosphate buffer pH 7.4 and phosphate buffer pH 6.8 prepared with drug solutions of known concentrations. The absorbance of each solution was measured separately at λ_{max} (242 nm) for 0.1N HCl solution, phosphate buffer pH 7.4 and phosphate buffer pH 6.8 respectively for dexamethasone.

Evaluation of powder blend:

Powder mixture were transferred to the amber coloured bottle to protect the light sensitive dexamethasone from light for turbular mixing till half an hour. Micrometric properties [such as bulk density and Carr's index] evaluated and uniformity of mixing was assessed by conducting powder content uniformity test on the powder mix samples before punching of tablets (**Table 2**). [Samples collected from final powder blend (1 to 3 times unit dose) using a thief from 10 different locations (5 from top, 3 from middle and 2 from bottom) for blending uniformity test]. For precompression evaluation, the powder mix was subjected to micrometric evaluation (bulk density and Carr's Index) and drug content uniformity to check the mixing uniformity. The loose bulk density (LBD), tapped bulk density (TBD) and Carr's Index (percentage compressibility) were found 0.3030 to 0.4764 gm/ml, 0.4464 to 0.6896 gm/ml, and 30.96 to 34.48%. The matrix formulations showed the high Carr's Index values, that indicating low compressibility of powder mix. The powder mix was found to contain 98.94 to 100.17% of the labeled

amount indicating uniformity of drug content that proved mixing efficiency.

Evaluation of colon targeted matrix tablet:

The guar gum-based matrix tablets and immediate release (reference formulation) were prepared by applying 7 ton (7000 kg) and 0.5 ton (500 kg) pressure respectively to get the disintegration time less than 60 seconds, and the hardness of the tablets was found to be in range of 0.43 to 5.74 kg/cm² and 4.30±0.296 kg/cm² respectively. Dexamethasone guar gum-based matrix tablets containing various proportion of guar gum ranging from 40 to 80% of guar gum and immediate release (reference formulation) containing 5% sodium starch glycolate (superdisintegrant at 5% level) were prepared and were subjected to thickness test, diameter test, weight variation test, hardness test, friability test and drug content uniformity test, and tablets were found to be in range of 3.19±0.020 to 3.62±0.049 (mm), 10.04±0.008 to 10.11±0.008 (mm), 346.91±1.218 to 353.00±0.892 (mg), 0.43±0.210 to 5.74±0.309 (kg/cm²), 0.223 to 2.961% and drug content uniformity 99.22 to 100.34% of the labeled amount respectively. All the tablet formulations passed the above tests except formulation DXCT5, which failed the friability test. Prepared tablets were subjected to measurement of mass degree of swelling and gel strength was found to be in the range of 2.68 to 3.70 and 5.21 to 15.50 (ml) respectively. The swelling of the guar gum-based formulations found linear with increasing percentage of guar gum.

The matrix tables containing 70 and 80% of guar gum (DXCT4 and DXCT5) showed high friability (0.702% and 2.961% respectively) and low hardness 1.67±0.173 kg/cm² and 0.43±0.210 kg/cm² respectively). This might be due to higher guar gum content in the matrix tablets. Hence, the DCT4 and DCT5 formulations were not subjected to in-vitro drug release studies.

The matrix tablets containing 40 to 60% were subjected to in-vitro release studies in 0.1N HCl (2 h), pH 7.4 Sorensen's phosphate buffer (3 h) and simulated colonic fluids (rat caecal content medium at 4% w/v level after 7 days of enzyme induction). It was reported earlier that the rat caecal content medium at 4% w/v level after 7 days of enzyme induction provide the best conditions for assessing the susceptibility of guar gum to colonic bacterial degradation. Dexamethasone tablets containing 40 to 60% of guar gum retained their physical integrity up to 24 h of dissolution study conducted without rat caecal contents in the dissolution medium (control).

Matrix tablets containing 40% of guar gum (DCT1) degraded into 2-3 pieces at about 10 h of dissolution study in the presence of simulated colonic fluids (rat caecal content medium). The percent of dexamethasone released from the DCT1 matrix tablets at the end of 24 hrs was found to be $100.74 \pm 0.251\%$. Whereas in control study (without rat caecal contents in the dissolution medium) only $77.95 \pm 1.268\%$ of dexamethasone was released. The study shows that the release of dexamethasone in the physiological environment of colon is due to the microbial degradation of guar gum matrix tablets in the presence of rat caecal contents. The dissolution study was carried out without rat caecal contents (control study) to ensure that the drug release is not due to mechanical erosion that is likely to occur because of the bowel movements in humans. On exposure to the dissolution fluids, the guar gum gets hydrated and forms a viscous gel layer that slows down further seeping-in of dissolution fluids towards the core tablet. The hydration of guar gum seems not to be affected by the pH of the dissolution medium.

On increasing the amount of guar gum in the matrix tablets, the release of dexamethasone decreased at the end of 24 h of dissolution study. The cumulative percent of dexamethasone released from matrix tablets containing 50% of guar gum (DXCT2) is released $99.47 \pm 0.338\%$ of dexamethasone in the presence of rat caecal contents whereas in control study the formulation released only $47.20 \pm 0.608\%$ of dexamethasone. A significant difference ($p < 0.0001$) was observed at 24h in the amount of dexamethasone released from DCT2 when compared to dissolution study without rat caecal contents.

The cumulative percent of dexamethasone released from matrix tablets containing 60% of guar gum (DCT3) released only $61.53 \pm 1.235\%$ of dexamethasone in rat caecal content medium at the end of 24 h whereas in control study it was only $24.97 \pm 0.185\%$. Though the matrix formulation DCT3 released only $61.53 \pm 1.235\%$ of dexamethasone in simulated colonic fluids, a significant difference was observed ($p < 0.0001$) in the dissolution pattern at 24h of study when compared to the dissolution study without rat caecal contents.

An immediate release dexamethasone tablet was formulated in the laboratory and used as a reference formulation to find the difference in the in-vitro release profiles of the drug. Almost the entire quantity of the drug was released within 2h (about 95.5%) of dissolution study. The matrix formulation DCT1 released almost the entire quantity of the drug

within 18 h of the dissolution. The formulation DCT2 also released about 99.47% of its drug content at the end of 24 h of dissolution study whereas the formulation DCT3 released only 61.53%.

It is clear from these results that DCT2 could target dexamethasone to colon because as it released almost the entire quantity at the end of 24 h of study. The DCT3 tablets are also considered as potential formulations for targeting of dexamethasone to colon because of the fact that the human caecal contents would be far richer in enzymatic activity than what was used in the present study. However, the relative potential of formulation DCT2 and DCT3 need to be evaluated in human volunteers.

In the present study dexamethasone was formulated as matrix tablets. Alternatively, dexamethasone tablets could have been coated with guar gum in the form of compression coat as mentioned earlier report. But in the present study, it was felt not necessary since only 15% of dexamethasone was released in the physiological environment of stomach and small intestine, while but releasing major portion (about 85%) of the drug in the physiological environment of colon.

The results of the in-vitro drug release study indicated that matrix tablets of dexamethasone containing 50% of guar gum is a potential formulation for targeting dexamethasone to the physiological environment of colon. The usefulness of this formulation (DXCT2) in the humans is needs further studies.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

Colonic drug delivery is a relatively recent approach to the treatment of diseases such as ulcerative colitis, Crohn's disease and irritable bowel syndrome. Such local treatment has the advantage of requiring smaller drug quantities, possibly leading to a reduced incidence of side effects and drug interactions. The most promising of the colonic drug delivery systems that are dependent on the enzymatic action of colonic bacteria are those based on polysaccharides. The polysaccharides are biodegradable, abundantly available and also cheap. The present study was aimed at developing novel dexamethasone formulation for colon targeting using guar gum in the form of a matrix tablet. It was reported earlier that guar gum could be used as carrier for colon-specific drug delivery in the form of either a matrix tablet or as a compression coat over a drug core tablet. The results of the in-vitro drug release study indicated that matrix tablets of dexamethasone containing 50% of guar gum is a potential formulation for targeting

dexamethasone to the physiological environment of colon. The usefulness of this formulation (DXCT2) in the humans is needs further studies.

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Table 1: Composition of dexamethasone matrix tablets and IR tablet

Ingredients	Quantity (mg)					
	DCT1	DCT2	DCT3	DCT4	DCT5	DCT6
Dexamethasone	10	10	10	10	10	10
Guar gum	140	175	210	245	280	--
Sodium starch glycolate (dry)	--	--	--	--	--	30
Microcrystalline cellulose (M.C.C.)	190	155	120	85	50	300
Talc	5	5	5	5	5	5
Magnesium Stearate	5	5	5	5	5	5
Total (mg)	350	350	350	350	350	350

Table 2: Micrometric Evaluation of Powder Mix

S. No.	Formulation Code	Mass of Powder (gms)	Volume of Packing (ml)	Taped Volume of Packing (ml)	LBD (gm/ml)	TBD (gm/ml)	Carrís Index (%)	Percent Drug Content (Powder mix) (%) Mean±SD (n=10)
1	DCT1	5	14.5	9.5	0.3448	0.5263	34.49%	99.82±0.674
2	DCT2	5	13	8.75	0.3846	0.5714	32.70%	100.11±0.700
3	DCT3	5	13	8	0.3846	0.625	38.40%	100.17±0.915
4	DCT4	5	11	7.5	0.4545	0.666	31.80%	99.93±0.0647
5	DCT5	5	10.5	7.25	0.4761	0.6896	30.90%	98.94±0.864
6	DCT6	5	16.5	11	0.303	0.4545	33.30%	100.05±0.569

Table 3: Physical properties of prepared colon targeted matrix tablet

S. No.	Formulation Code	Tablets Thickness (mm) Mean±SD (n=10)	Tablets Diameter (mm) Mean±SD (n=10)	Tablets Weight Variation (mg) Mean±SD (n=10)	Hardness (kg/cm ²) Mean±SD (n=10)	Friability (%) (n=10)	% Drug Content (tab) Mean±SD (n=10)	Mass Degree of Swelling (Q)*
1	DCT1	3.196±0.020	10.049±0.008	350.79±0.5906	5.74±0.309	0.282	100.13±1.263	2.68
2	DCT2	3.269±0.020	10.05±0.010	351.89±1.302	4.99±0.234	0.421	99.94±0.639	2.94
3	DCT3	3.28±0.024	10.06±0.006	350.59±3.181	4.56±0.297	0.503	100.03±0.893	3.15
4	DCT4	3.36±0.020	10.08±0.006	351.97±1.658	5.67±0.173	0.702	100.34±0.583	3.48
5	DCT5	3.4±0.016	10.11±0.008	346.91±1.218	5.43±0.210	2.961	99.225±1.140	3.7
6	DCT6	3.62±0.049	10.06±0.004	353±0.892	4.8±0.296	0.223	101.04±0.727	0.11

Figure 1: Zero-order kinetic plot of colon targeted matrix tablet and immediate release tablet (DCT1-DCT6)